

Wear Studies of Gel Cast Silicon Nitride Ceramics and Effect of Wear Parameters by Anova

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ABSTRACT

Amongst a broad group of engineering ceramic materials which combine low density with very good mechanical properties in a wide temperature ranges, nitrides are of particular importance. Tribological component materials demanding high reliability in the use are presently available and might be applied in various severe wear, thermal and mechanical applications. In the Present work aims to preparation of silicon nitride wear samples by gel casting method and it continues to determination of affect of input parameters sliding distance, sliding speed and load applied on the output wear rate of silicon nitride ceramics. An attempt has been made to study the effect of wear parameters like applied load, sliding speed and sliding distance on the dry sliding wear of Silicon nitride ceramics. Wear tests of the Silicon nitride ceramics are carried out on pin-on-disc wear testing machine by varying the sliding speed (1m/s, 2m/s and 3m/s), sliding distance (600m, 1000m, 1200m, 1500m and 1800m) and applied load(20N, 30N and 40N). The effect of these parameters on wear rate has been determined by using ANOVA analysis.

Keywords: ceramic material, silicon nitride, gelcasting, pin-on-disc wear testing machine

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a systematic analysis of wear prediction on advanced ceramics as an example to illustrate a viable wear prediction methodology. Advanced ceramics possess a unique combination of light weight, hardness, and chemical inertness. Thus they are often used in wear resistant applications. Their inherently brittle nature, however, creates a concern for potential premature catastrophic failures. Recent field success of ceramics in engines (water pumps seals, cam roller lifters, and wear pads), industrial pumps, and seals have alleviated many of these concerns. The strength and fatigue resistance of these materials have also increased substantially over the last decade.

The gelcasting process involves the preparation of aqueous slurry of ceramic powder, which contains small quantities of monomer, cross-linker, gel initiators, catalysts, sintering aids, and other additives the aqueous slurry of the ceramic powder is poured into a mold, and after drying removed from the mold.

Wear and Types of Wear:

According to ASTM International defines wear as "damage to a solid surface generally involving progressive loss of material, caused by the relative motion between that surface and a contacting substance or substances". In most instances, the material removal is a gradual process and the motion is a repetitive action. Wear is erosion of material from a solid surface by the action of another surface. It is related to surface interactions and more specifically to the removal of material from a surface as a result of mechanical action.

The basic types of wear found in the majority of engineering situations are as follows.

Classification of Wear

Objectives of the proposed work:

The main objective of this project is to gain comprehensive understanding of the fundamental principles in wear mechanism of gel casted specimens. The proposed works Starts from preparation of wear samples by gel casting method and research work continues to determination of affect of input parameters sliding distance, sliding speed and load applied on the output wear rate of silicon nitride ceramics alloy.

Table 1 Inputs and Outputs of the Proposed work

INPUT's	OUTPUT
Wear samples by gel casting	Actual Wear rate by Experiment
sliding distance	
sliding speed	
load applied	

Experiment Details:

Gel casting is a new method for fabricating ceramic bodies by means of polymerization through which a macromolecular network is created to hold the ceramic particles together

- ❖ Normally used Materials used in the preparation of ceramic slurry

S	Item	Justification
1	Silicon Nitride	The main constituent
2	Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	Sintering additive
3	Yttria (Y ₂ O ₃)	Sintering additive
4	Acrylamide	Gel-forming organic
5	Methacrylamide	Gel-forming organic
6	Metylenebisacryla	Cross linker
7	Dolapix CE64	Dispersant
8	Dolapix A88	Dispersant
9	Ammoniumpersulfa	Polymerization
1	Tetramethylethylen	Catalyst
1	Polyethylene glycol	To avoid surface

For gel casting purpose, acryl amide (AM, C₂H₃CONH₂) and N,N⁰-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAM, (C₂H₃CONH)₂ (CH₂)) were applied in the process of gel casting as monomers for polymerization. A dispersant (1 wt%, ammonium salt of poly (acrylic acid)) was added to minimize agglomeration, and

potassium persulphate (Merck, K₂S₂O₈) was used as initiator. A proper amount of polyacrylamide (PAM) was used for eliminating the surface exfoliation phenomenon of green body cast in air. Ammonia aqueous was used as pH adjuster. All of these reagents were chemically pure. Si₃N₄ powders (mean particle size: 0.37 μm, α phase (>94 wt %) employed in the experiment were commercially available materials. Al₂O₃ (mean particle size: 1.07 μm, 99% purity) and Y₂O₃ (mean particle size: 4.74 μm, 99.9% purity) were used as the sintering additive.

Figure 2 Wear test silicon nitride specimens

Pin-On-Disc Wear Testing Machine:

Generally there are two types of pin on disc machines. One type of typical system consists of a driven spindle and chuck for holding the revolving disc, a lever-arm device to hold the pin, and attachments to allow the pin specimen to be forced against the revolving disk specimen with a controlled load. In this project the machine used is IEICOS Wear and Friction Testing Machine.

ANOVA Analysis:

Minitab 16 has been used to find out significant factors and interactions from the experimental data. Three way interactions have been neglected. The analysis of variance for wear rate using adjusted SS values is shown in the below table. By the one-way Anova analysis the results for wear rate versus sliding speed, Load, sliding distance shown in below. From the above experiment details, the output wear rate is mainly affected by load and then sliding Distance and sliding speed.

Table 3 Wear Test Experiments Results

Sl No	Run Order	Sliding Speed (m/s)	Load (N)	Sliding Distance (m)	Wear time (sec)	Weight loss (mg)	Wear Rate (μg/s)
1	1	1	20	600	600	0.894	1.49
2	2	1	30	600	600	1.404	2.34
3	3	1	40	600	600	2.472	4.12
4	4	2	20	600	300	0.45147	1.5049
5	5	2	30	600	300	0.819	2.73
6	6	2	40	600	300	0.972	3.24
7	7	3	20	600	200	0.442	2.21
8	8	3	30	600	200	0.754	3.77
9	9	3	40	600	200	0.934	4.67
10	10	1	20	1000	1000	1.97	1.97
11	11	1	30	1000	1000	3.78	3.78
12	12	1	40	1000	1000	4.89	4.89
13	13	2	20	1000	500	0.91	1.82
14	14	2	30	1000	500	1.615	3.23
15	15	2	40	1000	500	2.125	4.25
16	16	3	20	1000	333.3	1.086	3.26
17	17	3	30	1000	333.3	1.373	4.12

18	18	3	40	1000	333.3	1.773	5.32
19	19	1	20	1200	1200	3.432	2.86
20	20	1	30	1200	1200	5.868	4.89
21	21	1	40	1200	1200	7.452	6.21
22	22	2	20	1200	600	1.524	2.54
23	23	2	30	1200	600	2.382	3.97
24	24	2	40	1200	600	3.222	5.37
25	25	3	20	1200	400	1.648	4.12
26	26	3	30	1200	400	1.856	4.64
27	27	3	40	1200	400	2.312	5.78
28	28	1	20	1500	1500	5.193	3.462
29	29	1	30	1500	1500	8.43	5.62
30	30	1	40	1500	1500	10.32	6.88
31	31	2	20	1500	750	2.67	3.56
32	32	2	30	1500	750	4.0725	5.43
33	33	2	40	1500	750	4.9125	6.55
34	34	3	20	1500	500	1.875	3.75
35	35	3	30	1500	500	2.325	4.65
36	36	3	40	1500	500	2.88	5.76
37	37	1	20	1800	1800	8.766	4.87
38	38	1	30	1800	1800	11.61	6.45
39	39	1	40	1800	1800	13.806	7.67
40	40	2	20	1800	900	4.284	4.76
41	41	2	30	1800	900	6.075	6.75
42	42	2	40	1800	900	6.606	7.34
43	43	3	20	1800	600	2.802	4.67
44	44	3	30	1800	600	3.072	5.12
45	45	3	40	1800	600	3.924	6.54

Figure 4 Wear rate vs sliding distance at speed 2 m/s

Figure 5 Wear rate vs sliding distance at speed 1 m/s

Figure 3 Main Effect Plot for Wear Rate

Results for wear rate versus sliding speed: $S = 1.623$ $R-Sq = 0.98\%$ $R-Sq(adj) = 0.00\%$

Results for wear rate versus Load: $S = 1.235$ $R-Sq = 42.64\%$ $R-Sq(adj) = 39.91\%$

Results for wear rate versus sliding distance: $S = 1.207$ $R-Sq = 47.83\%$ $R-Sq(adj) = 42.62\%$

By these results the percentage influence of input parameters on wear rate is first by sliding distance after that load and negligible effect by sliding speed.

Graphs of wear rate vs sliding distance:

The below graphs shows the response for sliding distance and wear rate at three load conditions for constant sliding velocity 1 m/s, 2m/s,3m/s respectively. The graph indicates as increasing load the wear rate is also increases for various sliding distance.

Figure 6 Wear rate vs sliding distance at speed 3 m/s

CONCLUSIONS:

The significant conclusion on the wear studies conducted on ceramic (Si_3N_4) based gel cast specimens regarding wear rate presented in the following sections.

- ❖ Gained the knowledge on gel casting manufacturing process and wear taking place of the ceramic specimens
- ❖ Wear testing samples are successfully prepared by near net shape method i.e. gel casting process.
- ❖ The wear studies is done on the ceramic (Si_3N_4) based gel cast specimens at different input parameters applied load, sliding speed and the sliding distance which are affects the amount of wear rate.
- ❖ From the minitab analysis table, the output wear rate is mainly affected by sliding distance and then Load and sliding speed.
- ❖ From the graphs, the wear rate increases with increases for a given sliding distance with increase in load and wear rate increases for a given load with increase in sliding distance.

SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK:

- ❖ In the present work, the studies related to wear properties were undertaken. Studies related to deformation fatigue characteristics, high temperature wear analysis, erosive wear and corrosive wear studies can also be carried out in future.
- ❖ In future, similar studies can be under taken at elevated temperatures which are of immense importance in aerospace and defense applications.

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